

ISic3356

I.Sicily inscription 3356

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.07.25; 2013.09.30 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Contrada Taracati (in a tomb previously robbed)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 24459

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μινύρα

2. Χαιρύλου

Apparatus

text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644861

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 387-388 fig.5
Libertini, G 1929. Il regio museo archeologico di Siracusa. *Guide dei musei*

italiani. Roma. At 122

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del
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